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Use of Ortho-substituted Benzalidenethiosemicarbazone in Gravimetric Determination of Palladium(II)

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DIMETHYL glyoxime and nioxime¹ have been used as analytical reagents for gravimetric determination of Pd(II). The present work with the reagents *o*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone was undertaken with a view to introduce these ligands for gravimetric determination of Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II). The precipitation of Ni(II) ion is complete at pH 2-3. Thus, these ligands have an edge over the ligand dimethylglyoxime and nioxime. It has also been found that platinum does not interfere as it does not form any precipitate at pH, 2-3.

Experimental

All reagents used were of AR grade. Stock solution of Pd(II) was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride in concentrated hydrochloric acid and water. 1% solution of the ligands was employed.

Preparation of Ligands: (a) *O*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone: It was prepared as described in the literature². (b) *O*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone: It was prepared by dissolving *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde in ethanol and treating it with thiosemicarbazone dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid. The ligand was obtained as a pale yellow precipitate which was recrystallised from ethanol and dried (m.p. 217°).

Determination of Palladium: A solution containing known amount of palladium(II) was diluted to 10 ml and was heated to 50-60°. The hot solution was treated with an alcoholic solution of the ligand followed by addition of sodium acetate when brown yellow precipitate in the case of *O*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone was obtained. The whole mass was digested on steam-bath for one

hour, filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed with hot water. The precipitate was dried in air over at 130-140° to constant weight, weighed as Pd(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ and Pd(C₈H₇N₃SCl)₂ respectively in the case of *o*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone. The results of some of the estimations are tabulated below:

TABLE

Sl. No.	Pd(II) taken (mg)	Pd(II) found (mg)		error	
		(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
1.	50	49.8	50.1	-0.4	+0.2
2.	40	40.1	40.1	+0.25	+0.25
3.	30	23.9	30.2	-0.33	+0.5
4.	20	20.1	19.9	+0.5	+0.5
5.	10	10.05	10.05	+0.5	+0.5

(a) With *o*-nitrobenzilidenethiosemicarbazone.
(b) With *o*-chlorobenzilidenethiosemicarbazone.

Determination of Pd(II) in the presence of other cations: Pd(II) is completely precipitated at pH=2-3 and Ni(II) is precipitated completely at pH=6-7. Thus it is easy to estimate palladium in the presence of Ni(II) and Cu(II). Pd(II) (30 mg) can be determined in the presence of 10 mg of Cu(II) and Ni(II), the maximum error being 1.5-2%.

Structure of the Chelates: *O*-substituted benzalidenethiosemicarbazones behave as bidentate ligands in neutral, ammoniacal and acid media. The chemical analysis of the complexes indicates that they have the chemical formula (I) Pd(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ and (II) Pd(C₈H₇N₃SCl)₂.

The complexes are diamagnetic. Their acetone solutions show maximum absorption at about 15000 cm⁻¹. The magnetic behaviour and the electronic spectra⁴ suggest for square planar structure of the complex. The ir spectra of the complexes have been recorded to determine the nature of bonding in the complexes. The presence of a sharp band at 3050 cm⁻¹ both in ligand and the complexes indicates N-H frequency remains unchanged in the complexes. The decrease in stretching⁵⁻⁷ frequency from about 720-730 cm⁻¹ in the ligands to 630-640 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates M-S bonding. The presence of new bands⁸ at about 500 cm⁻¹ and 450 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates the coordination through N' and S. The presence of the bands at 830 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of uncoordinated nitrite group⁹.

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